

Assessing the Challenges of Voluntary Arbitration in Resolving Labour Disputes in Tanzania: Lessons from India

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Abstract:

This article examines the challenges involved in the use of the voluntary arbitration mechanism in resolving labour disputes in Tanzania. The study draws upon lessons from India. In a voluntary arbitration, the parties to the labour dispute submit it to a neutral, independent third-party for a binding decision. The article examined the current state of the law, identified the challenges involved in using it for labour arbitration, and made some recommendations for law reform. The article adopts the doctrinal research methodology which relies extensively on the primary and secondary sources of legal information.

Keywords: Voluntary Arbitration, Alternative Dispute Resolution, Labour disputes, Tanzania, India.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Tanzanian Employment and Labour Relations Act (hereinafter referred to as ELRA) outlines the objectives of the Act, which include establishing a framework for resolving disputes through mediation, arbitration, and adjudication. The ELRA also emphasises the importance of utilising Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) and, consequently, introduces a dispute resolution process under Part VIII of the Act, which details the primary dispute resolution mechanisms. The enactment of sections 94(1) and (2) of the Tanzania Employment and Labour Relations Act¹ has led to the introduction of voluntary arbitration as a mechanism for dispute resolution, enabling parties involved in labour disputes to settle their disputes through arbitration, as stipulated in their employment contract. Voluntary arbitration is a private process that can ensure that parties can have a peaceful resolution of their disputes under contractual terms. The initial agreement to arbitrate serves as an example of responsible bargaining.²

In India, voluntary arbitration is provided under Section 10A of the Indian Industrial Dispute Act.³ The Act establishes the provisions for implementing voluntary arbitration as a mechanism for resolving industrial disputes. The Industrial Disputes (Amendment and Miscellaneous Provisions) Act⁴ amends the Indian Industrial Disputes Act by adding section 10A,⁵ which establishes an effective mechanism for resolving industrial disputes through voluntary arbitration. Furthermore, sections 10A (1), (2), and (3) outline the requirements of arbitration agreements between employers and workers, as well as the procedures and obligations for these agreements to be forwarded to the Government for publication in the Official Gazette.

This article is organized into seven sections. The first section of the paper provides the introduction and background for the study. This is followed by the second section which examines the concepts of Alternative Dispute Resolution, voluntary arbitration and labour disputes. In section three, the paper analyses the regulatory regime for voluntary arbitration in Tanzania. It focuses on the constitution of Tanzania as well as the Tanzanian Employment and Labour Relations Act. Section 4 of the article examine the legal and institutional framework for voluntary arbitration in India. A brief examination

¹ Tanzanian Employment and Labour Relations Act Cap 366 R.E. 2023. Section 94(1) and (2) states that; This Act shall not prevent an agreement to submit a dispute to arbitration. (2) The provisions of the Arbitration Act, shall apply to any agreed submission of a dispute to arbitration provided that- (a) notwithstanding the provisions of section 3 of the Arbitration Act, any dispute may be submitted to arbitration.

² Friedman, A.V. (1964). Arbitration of Disputes over New Labour Contract Terms, 15 W. Rsr. L. Rev. 735. Available at: <https://scholarlycommons.law.case.edu/caselrev/vol15/iss4/7> Accessed on 1 May 2025.

³ The Indian Industrial Dispute (Amendment and Miscellaneous Provision) Act, Act No.36 of 1956.

⁴ The Indian Industrial Dispute Act, No. 36 of 1956.

⁵ Ibid section 10A, States that; Where any industrial dispute exists or is apprehended and the employer and the workmen agree to refer the dispute to arbitration, they may, at any time before the dispute has been referred under section 10 to a Labour Court or Tribunal or National Tribunal, by a written agreement, refer the dispute to arbitration and the reference shall be to such person or persons (including the presiding officer of a Labour Court or Tribunal or National Tribunal) as an arbitrator or arbitrators as may be specified in the arbitration agreement.

of the constitution of India, and the Indian Industrial Dispute (Amendment and Miscellaneous) Act is undertaken. This is followed by a section on the challenges involved in the use of voluntary arbitration for labour disputes. In section six, the article makes a case for the adoption of voluntary arbitration in labour disputes, while section seven concludes the paper with some recommendations.

2. CONCEPTUAL ANALYSES

2.1 Alternative dispute resolution

Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) encompasses a variety of techniques and strategies aimed at addressing legal disputes without resorting to litigation or the court. This typically involves mediation, arbitration, and several "hybrid" methods where a neutral party assists in resolving legal matters outside the traditional court system.⁶ Furthermore, ADR can be better understood as a variety of methods that act as substitutes for court litigation in settling disputes, typically involving the help and involvement of an unbiased and neutral third party.⁷ Generally, in Tanzania, the mechanisms or forms of ADR include negotiation, mediation, reconciliation, and arbitration.

2.2 Voluntary arbitration

Voluntary arbitration, as one of the methods for resolving industrial disputes, is advantageous because it relies on the concept of voluntarism and allows the involved parties to select their own trusted, impartial, and independent individual to settle their disagreements, thereby potentially fostering greater long-term industrial peace.⁸ Voluntary arbitration in labour law is a crucial component of alternative dispute resolution (ADR), enabling parties involved in industrial disputes to resolve their issues without resorting to the formal court system. It provides an effective, economical, and less confrontational approach to dispute resolution, which is especially crucial for upholding industrial peace and cooperation.⁹ In voluntary arbitration, the disputing parties submit their dispute to an independent and neutral third party for a final and binding decision, which is mainly said to be an award or decision.¹⁰

2.3 Labour dispute

A labour dispute refers to a situation where there is a disagreement over a particular issue or group of issues that creates a conflict between workers and employers, or where

⁶ Mnookin, R.H. (1998). Alternative Dispute Resolution. Harvard Law School. Available at: <https://scholar.google.com> accessed on 4 August 2025.

⁷ Bachawat's (2010), Law of Arbitration and Conciliation, 5th ed, Vol. 2, Lexis Nexis, Butterworths Wadhwa, pg 2505.

⁸ Dr.Smt. Ashwini, V.K., (2018). Voluntary Labour Research. UGC Approved Journal No.48514. Volume-7/Issue-8/May-2018.

⁹ Labour Law Blogs. (August 28, 2024). Voluntary Arbitration in Labour Law. Available at: <http://labbhoomi.com/voluntary-arbitration> . Assessed on 1 August ,2025.

¹⁰ Sarkar, U. (2022). Voluntary Arbitration. Available at: <https://blog.ipleaders.in> Accessed on 2 June 2025

grievances are presented by either party, or concerning which employees or employers show support for the claims or complaints of others.¹¹ Labour disputes in Tanzania are governed by the Tanzania Employment and Labour Relations Act.¹² Also, the law provides for the use of dispute resolution mechanisms, which include mediation, arbitration, voluntary arbitration, adjudication and dispute procedure in the collective agreement. Labour disputes are an inherent part of both the workplace and organisational life.¹³

3. EGAL FRAMEWORK FOR VOLUNTARY ARBITRATION IN TANZANIA

3.1 The Constitution of the United Republic of Tanzania

The Constitution is the grundnorm of the state.¹⁴ Thus, all other laws must conform to the Constitution.¹⁵ Article 107A (2) (d)¹⁶ provides that “In delivering decisions in matters of civil and criminal nature under the laws, the court shall observe the following principles, that is to say, to promote and enhance dispute resolution among persons involved in the disputes.” Generally, the Constitution provides the foundation of the legal framework for laws governing the voluntary arbitration mechanism in resolving labour disputes in Tanzania, as it emphasises promoting and enhancing the use of the dispute resolution.

3.2 Tanzania Employment and Labour Relations Act

The Tanzania Employment and Labour Relations Act¹⁷ establishes core labour rights, sets basic employment standards, provides a framework for collective bargaining, prevents and settles disputes, and addresses related matters. In addition, the Act under Part VIII provides for alternative dispute resolution mechanisms like mediation, arbitration, adjudication, and dispute procedure in a collective agreement. The Act under section 94 (1) and (2)¹⁸ provides for voluntary arbitration, where it provides that the law shall not prevent an agreement to submit a dispute to arbitration.

¹¹ ILO, (1993) Resolution concerning Statistics of Strikes, Lockouts and other Action Due to Labour Disputes, at p 2

¹² Tanzanian Employment and Labour Relations Act CAP 366 R.E 2023

¹³ Zhou, L., Xi, M., Zhang, X. and Zhao, S. (2017). Labour relations conflict in the workplace: Scale development, consequences and solutions.

¹⁴ The constitution of United Republic of Tanzania 1977, as amended, *which states that, In delivering decisions in matters of civil and criminal nature in accordance with the laws, the court shall observe the following principles, that is to say to promote and enhance dispute resolution among persons involved in the disputes.*

¹⁵ Mpogole, M. (November-December 2023). An Examination of the Effectiveness of Labour Laws on Dispute Settlement Mechanisms for Public Servants in Tanzania. 2nd Year Master of Laws (LLM) from the St. Augustine University of Tanzania, Tanzania. Journal of Legal Studies and Research. Volume 9, Issue 6- ISSN 24552437. November-December 2023. Available at: www.thelawbrigade.com pg 162-177. Accessed on 6 April 2025.

¹⁶ The Constitution of the United Republic of Tanzania 1977 as amended.

¹⁷ Tanzanian Employment and Labour Relations Act [CAP 366 R.E 2023], *Supra*.

¹⁸ *Ibid*.

4. LEGAL AND INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK OF VOLUNTARY ARBITRATION IN INDIA

4.1 The Constitution of India, as amended in 2024

The Constitution of India is the supreme law of India. The Constitution defines the frameworks for the constitution, structure, procedures, powers, and responsibilities of administrative authorities, as well as the basic rights, guidelines, and responsibilities of citizens.¹⁹ The Preamble of the Constitution of India has enshrined its goals of social and economic justice to be achieved by every citizen of India. Currently, unquestionably, the goal of the State is to attain economic and social justice for everyone.²⁰ In addition, the Constitution of India acts as an instrument for government operations. To establish a state governed by the rule of law, it needs to be firmly rooted in the Constitution, which outlines the interactions among different branches of government and between the government and the citizens.²¹

4.2 The Indian Industrial Dispute (Amendment and Miscellaneous Provisions) Act²²

The Indian Industrial Disputes Act, 1947, was enacted to provide for the investigation and settlement of industrial disputes and certain other related matters.²³ The Act provides several dispute resolution procedures to address or settle this matter amicably. Conciliation, adjudication, and arbitration are some of these techniques.²⁴ However, before 1947, Industrial Disputes in India were handled according to the Indian Trade Disputes Act, 1929, which proved to be substantially inadequate in many respects as time went on.²⁵

Basically, in response to various criticisms of the machinery of conciliation and adjudication, Section 10A concerning voluntary arbitration was introduced through the

¹⁹ Dr. (Lt Col) Balhera, A., Dr.Kumar.A.(09 Dec 2022). Constitutional Amendments: Wounds on the soul of the original Indian Constitution. International Journal for Research in Engineering Application & Management (IJREAM). ISSN: 2454-9150.VOL-08, Issue -09, Dec 2022. Available at: DOI:10.30291/2454-9150.2022.0505

²⁰ Adv. Malegaonkar, S. (2018). Machineries for Settlement of Indian Industrial Disputes. Bharati Law Review, April – June, 2018.

²¹ Bhat, R.M. (2022). Historical Review of the Indian Constitution. Traditional Journal of Law and Social Sciences (TJLSS). Volume 01, Issue 02,2022, Pg 100-110.Available at: <https://traditionaljournaloflaw.com/journal> accessed on 3 September 2025.

²² The Indian Industrial Dispute (Amendment and Miscellaneous Provisions Act,1956, Act No.36 of 1956

²³ The Indian Industrial Disputes Act,1947, Act No.14 of 1947.

²⁴ Goel, R. (2024). Industrial Disputes in India and Settlement Mechanism. Student at Law College Dehradun, Uttaranchal University, Uttarakhand, India. International Journal of Law Management & Humanities [ISSN 2581-5369].

²⁵ Aryan, G. (2025). From the Indian Industrial Dispute Act,1947, to the Industrial Relations Code,2020: Aleap A heard or A Step Back in Back in Labour Dispute Resolution? India Journal of Legal Review (IJLR),5(1). Pg 790-800, APIS-3920-0001&ISSN-2583-2344.

Indian Industrial Disputes Miscellaneous Provisions (Amendments) Act,1956. The amendments aimed to give legal recognition to the system of voluntary arbitration.²⁶

5. CHALLENGES TO THE EFFECTIVENESS OF VOLUNTARY ARBITRATION IN RESOLVING LABOUR DISPUTES

Several problems arise from the use of arbitration to resolve labour disputes in Tanzania. This is more prominent due to the absence of specific regulations governing the procedures for using the voluntary arbitration mechanism. This has led to a challenge to the selection of arbitrators, as there are no specific guidelines on the modalities for the selection of arbitrators, which may result to partiality and lack of expertise. Furthermore, there are no specific regulations outlining procedures for enforcing the voluntary arbitration mechanism, and ELRA has only provided a section 94²⁷ for voluntary arbitration. However, it does not specify how it will be enforced for parties who use it to settle labour disputes, leaving parties in a dilemma. A reform of the legal regime to incorporate specific provisions on labour arbitration and enforcement will resolve this issue.

In the case of *Travel Port International Ltd Vs Precise Systems Ltd*,²⁸ the court held that the disputing parties must appear before the arbitral tribunal rather than the court when they have an existing agreement on referral to arbitration. Consequently, the principle of reparability is relevant as the arbitration clause is self-contained. Likewise, in Indian, in the case of *Karnal Leather Karamchari Sanghatan vs Liberty Footwear Company (Regd)*,²⁹ it was held that the requirement of publishing the arbitration agreement under Section 10-A (3) is mandatory and not directory, and non-compliance with the requirement contained in Section 10-A (3) is fatal to the arbitral award. The case emphasizes the importance of publishing the agreement of the parties when using voluntary arbitration to resolve labour disputes in India. Also, in the case of the *General Manager, Western Coalfields Ltd vs Sumit MULLICK and others (2012)*,³⁰ the Bombay High Court ruled that the remedies provided by Sections 10 and 10A are interchangeable. Therefore, after an arbitration agreement has been made, the government is not permitted to refer it to any of the authorities listed in section 10 of the Act.

²⁶ Siby, E.R. (May 7, 2020). Voluntary Arbitration under the Indian Industrial Disputes Act: A Critical Assessment.

²⁷ Tanzania Employment and Labour Relations Act [CAP 366 R.E 2023].

²⁸ Msc. Commercial Application No.359 of 2017.

²⁹ (1984) 4SCC448(India).

³⁰ No.2613 of 2001. Decided On: 28-09-2012.

6. THE CASE FOR VOLUNTARY ARBITRATION OF LABOUR DISPUTES

Voluntary arbitration offers several advantages over litigation in resolving labour disputes. Firstly, it is faster and more cost-effective. Litigation often involves lengthy court procedures, adjournments, and appeals, which delay justice and increase legal expenses.³¹ By contrast, arbitration provides a streamlined process where parties agree on procedural rules, allowing disputes to be resolved within a shorter timeframe and at reduced cost. Secondly, arbitration ensures flexibility and party autonomy. Parties can select arbitrators with expertise in labour relations, thereby ensuring that disputes are resolved by individuals with practical knowledge of industrial relations, unlike litigation where judges may not always possess specialized labour expertise.³² Thirdly, voluntary arbitration promotes confidentiality. Labour disputes often involve sensitive issues such as employee misconduct, financial records, or trade union strategies.

Court proceedings are public, whereas arbitration is private, safeguarding the parties' reputations and preserving trust in ongoing employment relations.³³ Fourthly, arbitration fosters industrial peace and relationship preservation. Litigation is inherently adversarial, often escalating conflict between employers and employees. Arbitration, however, is less confrontational, and because it is consensual, it encourages cooperation, mutual respect, and the possibility of maintaining long-term working relationships.³⁴ Additionally, arbitration provides finality of decisions. Unlike litigation, where appeals can prolong disputes indefinitely, arbitral awards are generally binding and enforceable, ensuring closure and stability for both employers and employees.³⁵ In Tanzanian jurisprudence has underscored this preference. In *Travel Port International Ltd v. Precise Systems Ltd*, the court affirmed that where parties have opted for arbitration, they must honour their agreement rather than seek court intervention. Therefore, voluntary arbitration stands out as a superior mechanism compared to litigation in labour disputes because it is efficient, specialized, confidential, relationship-preserving, and final qualities essential for fostering industrial harmony and upholding workers' rights while maintaining employers' operational stability.

7. CONCLUSION

Generally, the ELRA introduced a voluntary arbitration mechanism for resolving labour disputes in Tanzania. Nonetheless, the aims of this mechanism have not been effectively applied in Tanzania due to the challenges mentioned above. Consequently, there is a need for amendments to these provisions of the ELRA to enhance its functionality and effectiveness. First, amending the Tanzanian Employment and Labour Relations Act to

³¹ Bachawat, S.C., *Law of Arbitration and Conciliation* (5th ed., Vol. 2, Lexis Nexis Butterworths Wadhwa, 2010) 2505.

³² Mnookin, R.H., *Alternative Dispute Resolution* (Harvard Law School, 1998).

³³ Friedman, A.V., "Arbitration of Disputes over New Labour Contract Terms" (1964) 15 *W. Rsrv. L. Rev.* 735

³⁴ Siby, E.R., "Voluntary Arbitration under the Indian Industrial Disputes Act: A Critical Assessment" (2020).

³⁵ Aryan, G., "From the Indian Industrial Dispute Act, 1947, to the Industrial Relations Code, 2020: A Leap.

provide procedures and mechanisms for accommodating the use of voluntary arbitration mechanisms and their implementation. It is also necessary to enhance public awareness and promote the use of the voluntary arbitration mechanism in resolving labour disputes in Tanzania.